

POST-COLONIAL PROBLEMS OF ENGLISH LITERATURE IN THE MID-TWENTIETH CENTURY

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ABSTRACT

The article examines the problem of adaptation of English culture to the postcolonial situation of the middle of the twentieth century on the example of the novels of G. Green and E. Burgess. The variety of forms of hybrid identity is becoming one of the main themes of the "Malay Trilogy" by E. Burgess, whose novels are viewed as an intermediate stage between the colonial and the postcolonial novel itself in English literature.

Keywords: national identity problem, hybrid identity, postcolonial novel, E. Burgess, G. Green

Introduction.

The image of the East, created in the English novel of the 50-60s of the twentieth century, starts from the maxim set by R. Kipling: "The West is the West, the East is the East, and they will never come together ...". The opposition of the West and the East is defined in most works as the opposition of Chaos and Order, the opposition friend / foe is gradually blurred and replaced by the opposition me / the other. However, this is largely due to the erosion of the national community of English-Europeans - people of the West, who are assimilated in one form or another in the East, and not due to the recognition of the similarity of any characteristics of Western and Eastern people. Even if the impassability of the border between the Western man, the bearer of culture and the rational principle, and the Eastern man, the bearer of chaos and often base passions, is not directly asserted, it is implied a priori. We can say that the image of the East fits well into the framework that makes it possible to call it oriented towards the colonial stereotype, however, ideas about the East are characterized by internal development, which simultaneously presupposes a dynamic change in ideas about the national "we", or rather, the rejection of the category of national "we" in favor of the national "I", from collective identity in favor of an individual, unique national identity. We will consider these features of the postcolonial British novel on the example of the works of G. Green "Comedians", "The Quiet American" and E. Burgess "Malay Trilogy". Which allow us to call it oriented towards the colonial stereotype; however, ideas about the East are characterized by internal development, which at the same time presupposes a dynamic change in ideas about the national "we", or rather, the rejection of the category of the national "we" in favor of the national "I" benefit of an individual, unique national identity.

Discussion.

Already since the 30s in the work of G. Green (the novel "England gave birth to me") a special national type has been created, this is the type of hero "torn off" from the national soil, whose genetic connection with the homeland is determined by the powerful pressure of the Victorian stereotype on his mind. This stereotype can be both the subject of rejection ("Comedians", "The Quiet American"), and the subject of overcoming ("Traveling with Auntie"). One way or another, the hero is in constant dialogue with him, including with that part of him that dictates to the "real Englishman" an imperial sense of superiority over the aborigines, each of whom in one way or another evokes in the national memory the image of Shakespeare's heroes. Despite the quite tolerant attitude of G. Green's heroes to foreign culture, the designation of her strangeness is always present in the author's novels. In all

the works that take place in the countries of the East, there is a clear division into those who are part of the European (and American) world, and the local population. The central heroes of the novels (*Brown in Comedians*, *Fowler in The Quiet American*) are adapted to the world of the East, but are not dissolved in it, they still feel like a part of the Western, Christian world, but are in a state of constant internal conflict with the collective "we" nation, which manifests itself in the clichéd, caricatured images of compatriots or brothers in the European world. Not to the same extent as in the works of the 19th century, but in the novels of G. Green there is still a rapprochement of the people of the East and the South with the natural world (comparison with a monkey), there is an exotic element in the image of this world. In "Comedians", for example, a voodoo rite is described with the obligatory biting off of the head of a live rooster. Each of the two worlds - aborigines and Europeans - is conflicted inside, but the designation of the alienation of these worlds is constantly present. So, the love relationship between a white and a black or a Vietnamese and a white is perceived as an expression of eccentricity ("Traveling with Aunt," "The Quiet American"), the most frequent type of relationship between representatives of different worlds is the relationship between the master and the servant (Brown and Joseph in "Comedians", Wordsworth and Aunt Augusta in *Journey with Aunt*). As in the novels of R. Kipling and E. Forster, the theme of the guilt and responsibility of the Western man appears in the novels of G. Green, but the hero of G. Green is an individualist, which, even when making a certain political choice ("The Quiet American"), is not part of the world of political struggle. In general, we can say that the Victorian model in the depiction of the East in G. Green's novels, although it becomes an object of overcoming, still retains its influence, generating an internally conflicting perception of one's own identity.

In the work of Anthony Burgess, new trends appear in the depiction of the world of the East. The trilogy by E. Burgess, entitled "The Malay Trilogy" by himself, is one of the early works of the author. Three novels, "Time for a Tiger" (1956), "The Veiled Enemy" (1958) and "Oriental Beds" (1959), were written from the impressions of his own stay in the country, which he left in 1959, when doctors suspected he had a tumor in the brain. In these novels one can observe the emergence of the problems that characterize the postcolonial discourse of British literature. One of these problems is the relationship between East and West, which occupied E. Burgess in the first decades of his work, perhaps more than others. The Burgess trilogy is one of those works who are beginning to develop postcolonial problems in English literature, so it is of interest primarily from the point of view of how the answers to traditional questions of this problematic questions about the relations of peoples after the colonial era, about the traces left by the outgoing colonialists, are born. The author of the trilogy manages to avoid demonstrating a purely colonialist position, showing the versatility of the relationship between the British and representatives of the colonies. The theme of Malaya is not new in English literature, it appears, for example, in the work of S. Maugham's "On the outskirts of the empire", but this work mainly represents the world of the British. In this sense, on the one hand, E. Burgess's novel is in many ways progressive for the literature of its time, if only because it avoids a sharp division of heroes into "then we are faced with the problem of self-determination of representatives of another camp, the best of who are trying to be objective. The questions that E. Burgess considers in his novels are in many ways completely new for the literature on colonies, which is due to the author's excellent acquaintance with modern theoretical research, and E. Burgess even anticipates some of them. In particular, this is manifested in a clear linking of the problem of national identity with issues of language.

The Malay Trilogy allows us to observe the creative evolution of the writer, which is evident from novel to novel. The first novel, *Time for a Tiger*, provides a clear understanding of the author's literary sources. The very formulation of the problem of East and West undoubtedly goes back to R. Kipling. Two characters - an Englishman - are "driven" by two main Kipling themes: police officer Nabby Adams, yearning for life in India and as a result, returned to Bombay, and soldier Major Rivers, recalling his service in Africa and promoting cruelty [De Vitis, 1972]. In the poems of the protagonist's wife, Fenella Crabbe, Eliot intonations are clearly audible. The approach to solving the main problem, according to critics, allows us to talk about associations with the recently published novel by Graham Green "*The Quiet American*" [Coale, 1981]. The political situation in the first novel has not yet developed, and the comic element is less pronounced. The problem of British assimilation in Malaya is largely associated with the problem of language and is sometimes identified with it. So, Nabby Adams, who knows Punjabi and Indian dialects, cannot and does not want to live in Malaya, aiming for Bombay. The hero's wife, Fenella Crabbe, feels like a stranger. The desire of the central hero to assimilate in the country is connected, among other things, with the desire to learn the language. Understanding the country and posing one of the main problems of the novel, quite traditional for the literature of this period, the opposition of East and West as Chaos and Order is also associated with

language: "There are no rules ... this is the first thing you need to learn. Each word is different from any other. Words you need to memorize one by one. The English are always looking for some rules, but here, due to this, possible approaches to solving the problem of identity are complicated. However, the principle of the absence of rules turns out to be very important both for the depiction of the East as a chaotic world, and to some extent for the depiction of the colonists, each of whom demonstrates a special type of attitude to the situation, practically not duplicating each other. Due to this, possible approaches to solving the problem of identity are complicated. However, the principle of the absence of rules turns out to be very important both for the depiction of the East as a chaotic world, and to some extent for the depiction of the colonists, each of whom demonstrates a special type of attitude to the situation, practically not duplicating each other.

The portrait of the East in the trilogy is diverse. Already in the first novel, two tendencies for evaluating the East are outlined: the first tendency is the portrayal of Asians as primitive, pompous and stupid creatures. Mainly those representatives of the Malay peoples who profess Islam tend to this type. Their nationality may vary. In the first novel, it is the Punjabi Alladad Khan, in the second - the prominent Malay official Aban, in the third - the Malay Seyid Omar. All representatives of this type have large families, whose numbers are due to the tradition of polygamy, and no less numerous relatives. The main motive that unites this group is the motive of lust in all its senses. All representatives of this group are distinguished by greed; all of them (except for Seid-Omar, whom Jamil duplicates in this sense in the third book) are attracted to women other than their wives. In the first two novels, this is the classic situation of attraction to a white woman, the wife of Victor Krabbe. In the third volume, the situation becomes more complicated and the main sexual object becomes Rosemary, who embodies a certain type of emancipated Asian woman.

This first type of oriental hero, perceived, apparently, negatively, demonstrates its resilience in the world of Malaya, since its representatives have numerous offspring. In the third novel, the son of Seyid Omar, Seyid Hasan, occupies a rather significant place in the work and is portrayed as one of the main representatives of the future independent country. His ignorance and complacency is the constant subject of the author's irony. Representatives of the peoples of India and Ceylon, who in the novel are already becoming clearly comic characters, belong to the same type. It is interesting that the more relevant for a particular character or group of characters the division of friend / foe according to the national, confessional or even caste principle, the more reduced this character becomes, the more often he acts as a hero of ridiculous, comic situations. So, in the second novel, the comic group of eternally drunken idlers is represented by the Sikhs, for whom caste affiliation is essential, in the third - by the Tamils. They stick together, find themselves in comic situations, but persistently adhere to prejudices and believe in their exclusivity (for example, Mohinder Singh loses half of the store, while continuing to consider himself a smart merchant, Tamils avoid marrying representatives of other nations, which leads one of them to an unhappy and hopeless love).

The second trend is the portrayal of the East as a carrier of an exotic, strange, incomprehensible and terrible mentality. The main motive leading this topic is the motive of deception, betrayal, which is not recognized by the traitors themselves as such. This group of images is distinguished by individualization, they are not similar to each other. In the first novel, this theme is associated with the image of Krabbe's servant, the homosexual Ibrahim, who constantly robbed the owner, and at the end escapes from him, and the hero's students, Chinese boys Tun Chong and Shu Hong, who cover up their own rebellious moods, accusing teacher Krabbe of initiating riots at school. The same theme in the second novel is supported by the image of the cook Krabbe Ha-Vinh, who makes his master an involuntary companion of the communist rebels, as well as the images of robbers. The theme of betrayal in its various forms becomes the dominant theme of the second novel and is also associated with the image of Rupert Hardman, an albino Englishman who decided to naturalize in Malaya by marrying a local woman who unwittingly betrays Krabbe by telling Jaganathan about his past sympathies for Marxism. In the third book, the topic of betrayal weakens, manifesting itself in a somewhat more complex form in the history of Krabbe's relationship with the Chinese boy Robert Loo, who is a talented composer, but does not see the need for recognition of his talent, thereby deceiving Krabbe's hopes.

A special place among the images of the second type belongs to the image of Chi Norma, Hardman's eastern wife, who represents the "reverse side" of the type of Muslim woman, powerless in society, but omnipotent in the family. "Chi Nor Ma was a good Malay, a good Muslim, that is, she came from the Ache family, came from northern Sumatra, she herself from time to time liked to wear European dress, drank strong with pink gin, showed ignorance about the content of the Koran ... Two

husbands - the first Dutchman, the second Englishman - wasted away from the unpredictable outbursts of her passion and expansive sexual requests "[Coale, 1981].

Both of these types of oriental heroes are devoid of reflection, therefore, the problem of any self-identification does not bother the diverse representatives of the world of Malaya, being reduced only to the pre-doomed desire of some of them not to mix with other peoples, to preserve racial exclusivity, which receives a comic interpretation in the images of Tamils in the third novel, none of which for this reason can marry and seeks to prevent the others from marrying. The problem of self-identification and, in general, any reflection is manifested only in the characters of those Asian heroes, in whose veins a different blood already flows, especially the blood of Europeans. This is the aforementioned Roper, Abdul Qadir, a mixture of Malay, Chinese and Dutch, who gravitated towards asking provocative questions like: "Why are we letting whites stay with us?"

The problem of identity, the search for their place in Malaya, is connected in the novel mainly with the world of the British and other Europeans, whose positions on this issue range from the desire to immediately leave Malaya (Fenella Krabbe) to the desire to merge with it (Roper, Hardman). The path to finding your dream turns out to be paradoxical. Unappreciated in Malaya even by her own husband, the beautiful poet Fenella Krabbe is forced to meet with the Malay official Aban in order to achieve her goal - to return to her homeland.

A special case is presented by "false" identities, when the representatives of Europe begin to identify themselves with Asia or vice versa. Interesting in this sense is the case of Nabby Adams, an Englishman who felt the best in India and dreams of returning there: "You are definitely an Englishman, but you have forgotten how to speak the damn language. Understand for God's sake" [Ashcroft, 1989]. The case of Nabby Adams is no exception among the colonists: "Nobody cares, no one wanted to consider the premises a home. Nabby Adams strove to Bombay, Flaherty was eager to Palestine, Keir would soon return to Glasgow, Vorpole started a Chinese widow in Malacca" [Coale, 1981] ... As in the novel of the early twentieth century, the change of identity is assessed negatively here,

However, unlike his predecessors, E. Burgess introduces the opposite situation. The image of Rosemary in the third novel of the trilogy becomes a striking example of the "opposite" result of general confusion. A beauty, whose ideal beauty the author repeatedly calls absurd or ridiculous, dark-skinned, outwardly true representative of Asia, she yearns for England as her homeland, dreaming of marrying only an Englishman: a princess who married a mere mortal, who condescends to cook special dishes - exotic, spicy - for guests, but the rest of the household is entrusted to British servants. Besides, she is, of course, a Javanese princess, or Balinese, or Hawaiian, but not a woman of color. [Burgess, 2002]

The main bearer of British national consciousness in the novel is the protagonist himself, Victor Krabbe. It is the picture of the world that is presented in Krabbe's reasoning that is the main one in the novel, although not final. As S. Caul notes in his book about E. Burgess, "... the only character representing order is trying to bring stability and understanding to the racially, religiously and culturally mixed world around it" [Mohan, 1997]. Indeed, Krabbe is trying to bring culture and enlightenment to the world of Malaya in accordance with his understanding. He is aware of himself as the bearer of a certain educational, purely British cultural mission, thereby realizing one of the essential aspects of national identity (D. Miller defines it as follows: "Since our ancestors worked and shed blood, in order to create and protect a nation, we, those who belong to it by birthright, inherit the obligation to continue their cause" [Lok, 2020]). However, the reality of the East resists the rationalistic ideas of the West (represented by Krabbe). The confusion of Malaya manifests itself more within the school, restrained by British control, then in the third novel, associated with the era of Malaya's independence, it unfolds throughout the country. "True, there was an illusion of harmony with complete British control. But self-determination is a laughable thought in a country with such a mixed population. There are no people here. There is no common culture, language, religion, literature" [El_Kaidi, 2022]. However, the reality of the East resists the rationalistic ideas of the West (represented by Krabbe). If in the first novel the national and political confusion of Malaya manifests itself more within the school, restrained by British control, then in the third novel, associated with the era of Malaya's independence, it unfolds throughout the country. "True, there was an illusion of harmony with complete British control. But self-determination is a ridiculous idea in a country with such a mixed population. There is no person here. There is no common culture, language, religion, literature" [Vermeulen, 2006].

The opposition of East and West, as opposition of Chaos and Order, on the one hand, is very close to the author of the novel, but the plot-wise, objectively emerging picture contradicts this concept, placing the bearer of British national consciousness in the position of a failure. The

relationship of the hero, like other British people, with Malaya is already based not so much on the dichotomy of friend / foe as on the opposition I / others; its implementation sometimes leads to a lack of agreement between the colonists themselves, who include the concept of "other" and representatives of their own race. They find themselves, like the protagonist, absorbed by the very chaos of the East, into which they hoped to bring their own political and cultural order. The hero loses largely because of his emotional involvement in the situation in Malaya, precisely because he is trying to be useful to the country.

A different, reduced type of colonizer is represented by the images of the Americans replacing the British. For example, Temple Haynes, an American who appears in the third volume of the novel, demonstrates a "scientific" approach to Malaya. He "studies" the country in only one area (not knowing the Malay language, he studies its phonetics). The absurdity of this approach is demonstrated by a comic scene in which a young American shows the residents various images, wondering why they call everything in one word, until one of the British, who knows the language, explains to him that this word is "picture". Haynes is a representative of the race, in the words of Krabbe, "devoid of guilt, as well as a sense of history" [Popova, 2004], does not consider it necessary either to understand or love the country he came to, making it only an object of study.

Conclusion.

At the end of the novel, the author creates a pseudo-utopian picture of reconciliation of races, at least of the younger generation on the basis of the unification of culture, the culture that E. Burgess perceives as an Americanized culture, the culture of a consumer society (youth fashion, popular music), demonstrating, as in many English dystopias, lack of demand for cultural diversity, history in modern Americanized civilization [Watson, 1998].

And a picture of the diverse world of Malaya is created, all possible types of intra-eastern and inter-civilizational mixing (false identities) are emphasized, but the general binary picture of the world, characteristic of the colonial discourse, remains relevant. The West / East opposition remains unresolved in the Asia / Europe relationship, but is paradoxically resolved in the America / Asia relationship due to the loss of religious, spiritual culture, the important components of which were the feeling of guilt before the oppressed nation, an attempt to preserve cultural diversity, the special image of the country.

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